

The Role of Time Reversal and Possible Number of Reactions on Equilibrium Part 4

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In Parts 2 and 3, we focused exclusively on the idea of reaction balance being linked to a conserved statistical quantity, namely the number of possible successful ways to obtain successful reactions. We argued that a statistical balance or equilibrium occurs when the number of possible reactions of e_1, e_2 (the incoming colliding particles) matches that of e_i, e_j (the outcomes). At the same time, we suggested that this statistical balance must be taken together with conservation of energy (elastic collisions) $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$. Here we try to argue that a stronger statement is present. We suggest that equilibrium occurs when some kind of statistical quantity is conserved or balanced, but this balance must respect conservation of energy and particle number, i.e. intrinsically contain it in a function strictly of $p(e_i)$'s.

We note that one may write: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((1)), but if $p(e_i)$ is an equilibrium probability, then F is simply the inverse of p , rendering ((1)) an obvious statement which is not necessarily based on any kind of probability balance. We suggest that a statistical balance or conserved statistical quantity is created when equilibrium is established and that this statistical balance must be immune to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, while at the same time upholding conservation of energy $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}/N$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. We suggest that e_i must emerge from some kind of statistical function of $p(e_i)$'s alone, because the statistical balance may be written strictly in terms of $p(e_i)$'s, but must intrinsically contain conservation of energy.

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases, one may a priori create a statistical balance statement (reaction balance), namely that the number of possible e_1, e_2 successful interactions match those of e_i, e_j (but it is implicitly understood that $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$). Nevertheless, the matching equation must contain functions of $p(e_i)$ alone which represent energy because it implicitly contains energy conservation. We postulate that in equilibrium one may consider a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. One may immediately try to write: $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ ((2)) as representing a conservation of energy equation, but only if this expression is invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. At the same time $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ must be respected. In the MB case, ((2)) holds, but in the FD and BE cases, matters are more complicated. Multiple probabilities are present and so multiple (two) average terms are required: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i) + (1-p(e_i))) \ln(1-p(e_i))$ in the FD case, but there is still an $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, namely $\ln(p(e_i) / (1-p(e_i)))$. The point is that a statistical balance or conservation gives rise to an equilibrium scenario which respects conservation of energy and the number of particles.

As a result, we argue that even if one does not have a reaction balance statement or a factorial expression of number of states, one may introduce an entropy expression (conserved statistical quantity) which explicitly upholds conservation of energy and particle number as these are the only other conserved quantities in the system. In other words, a statistical balance is created which is invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, but at the same time must reveal conservation of energy and particle number.

In a number of previous notes, we introduced a function: $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ such that: $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$. Here we try to argue why such a function should exist. In Parts 2 and 3, we were able to link $G(p(e_i))$ to reaction balance, but what happens if there is no reaction balance or a priori factorial expression as in the Tsallis

case? We argue that the general idea of a statistical balance function which reveals conservation of energy and particle number may still be used and so is a general procedure.

Reaction Balance for the MB, FD and BE Cases

In Parts 2 and 3, we argued that a reaction balance equation captures a statistical conserved quantity while upholding conservation of particle number and conservation of energy. It is based on the kind of physical reactions which occur in a system. For the MB case, it is argued that for $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$, any e_1 may interact with any e_2 . Due to time reversal, the product:

$$N_1 * N_2 = N p(e_1) N p(e_2) \text{ must equal } N_i * N_j = N p(e_i) N p(e_j) \text{ (with } e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \text{ understood)} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, $N_1 * N_2$ is the conserved statistical quantity. It automatically contains particle number conservation because there are 2 particles on each side of ((3)). Furthermore, and this a key point we wish to express, ((3)) must implicitly contain energy conservation. In previous notes, we always wrote ((3)) together with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, but this seems to imply that conservation of energy is implicitly contained in ((3)), or in other words, there exists a function:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ where } F \text{ is strictly a function of } p(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is a strong statement, we suggest. One might at first argue that F is simply the inverse function of $p(e_i)$ for the equilibrium $p(e_i)$. We suggest, however, that something much more occurs here.

In the FD case: $N_1 (N - N_1) N_2 (N - N_2)$ is the conserved statistical quantity.

We argue that one must be able to write a function:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } G(p(e_i)) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) represents a statistical balance which marks equilibrium. ((5)) must be invariant to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which means that $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } dG/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$. At the same time, we argue that ((5)) must intrinsically conserve particle number and energy. In other words:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } dp(e_i) = 0 \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

must be buried within ((5)). It is this set of ideas which allow one to write:

$$\text{Sum over } dG(p(e_i)) = 0 = A \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dp(e_i) + B \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } dp(e_i) \quad ((7))$$

We have used ((7)) in numerous previous notes, but here we try to justify it. Even without reaction balance or factorial expressions, one should be able to consider an expression ((7)), if in fact energy and particle number conservation are the only two key features present.

We try to demonstrate the usefulness of the above ideas by applying them to Tsallis entropy.

Tsallis Entropy

In the case of Tsallis entropy, one has the constraints:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = \text{number } 1 \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((8))$$

The “catch” is that one does not have a readily identifiable reaction balance or factorial expression of a number of states. The Tsallis scenario does not make use of the usual \ln function used to break products of probabilities in a product reaction balance equation into sums which may be linked to e_i terms in order to enforce conservation of energy. (Particle number balance is already present in reaction balance.) This does not mean that ((8)) does not need to be enforced. It does. We argue that even though one does not have the usual interactions present, equilibrium should still be represented by a statistical balance or conserved quantity which is invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ and automatically carries the notion of ((8)), i.e. the two conservations present. Without an interaction reaction balance expression or a factorial expression (with Stirling’s approximation) one may write a priori:

$$\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = 0 = A \sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i + B \sum_i p(e_i) \quad ((9))$$

Now, given the absence of reaction balance, one has no idea whether there are multiple probabilities in the problem as in the FD or BE case. The simplest scenario is to suggest a single probability as in the MB case. In such a case, there should be an expression $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ such that one has an average quantity:

$$\sum_i G(p(e_i)) = \sum_i F(p(e_i)) p(e_i)^q = \sum_i (-e_i/T) p(e_i)^q \quad ((10))$$

((10)), however, is much more general than simply having a function which represents average equilibrium energy. It must hold for $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ and incorporate both energy and particle number conservation. Here $p(e_i)^q$ is the function used to create an average. Using ((10)):

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad (\text{i.e. } A = -1/T) \text{ and } p(e_i)^q dF/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad (B=1) \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{Then, } F(p(e_i)) = 1/(1-q) \{ 1 - p(e_i)^{1-q} \} \text{ such that } q \rightarrow 1 \text{ yields } \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((12))$$

In order to try to see some physics present in the above scenario, we consider the MB case. Imagine that one has N particles, each with the same energy E/N . Why is this not an equilibrium scenario? At first, $p(e_i) = 0$ unless $e_i = E/N$ in which case $p(E/N) = 1$. The problem is that this scenario is not stable under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. Some kind of statistical balance or conserved quantity must be established such that $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ leaves the system unchanged and respects conservation of particle number and energy conservation, i.e. implicitly contains them.

We suggest that a similar scenario exists in the Tsallis case. Imagine that one starts with the goal of achieving a total energy E at some time t . In particular, one might plant seeds in a series of different areas denoted by i . If a seed germinates in area i , then it will produce e_i of crop. Assume that there exists a probability $p(e_i)$ such that $p(e_i)^q$ is the probability that a seed becomes a stable seedling and goes on to produce e_i produce, where q is a known number. Then, in order to ensure that E_{total} is achieved, one must adjust $p(e_i)$ values. If one wishes to do this in a statistically stable way such that the result is invariant to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, then one needs an statistical conserved quantity which respects $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E/N$ or whatever conservation laws apply a priori. We try to explain why : $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i p(e_i) + B \sum_i p(e_i) = 0$ ((1)) holds a priori, as we have used this in a number of previous notes. We argue that there must exist a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ in order that energy (and hence energy conservation) emerge and that one may consider a statistical conserved quantity in terms of average values. Thus, one may try: $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. In the FD and BE cases, there are multiple probabilities (2), so two terms are needed. Ultimately there is still an $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ which emerges from the $dG(p(e_i))$ expression. In the Tsallis case, for which there is no immediate reaction balance or $\ln(\text{number of states})$ factorial expression using Stirling's approximation, the above idea still holds, but one uses $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E/N$ as the physical constraints. Thus, the idea of ((1)) seems to be a powerful approach to finding equilibrium $p(e_i)$ values, but does not need to be based on reaction balance or factorial (\ln number of states) schemes. It may be introduced a priori as described above, we argue.

We suggest that the idea of statistical conserved quantity which contains various physical conservation laws (such as particle number and energy) implicitly, may be more general than reaction balance and factorial expression which use Stirling's approximation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may consider an equilibrium in an abstract manner that goes beyond the usual reaction balance and $\ln(\text{states})$ factorial expressions using Stirling's approximation. We argue that physical processes may exist in a system which allows $p(e_i)$ values to change. Here we note that probability is directly associated with a value e_i (usually energy). When do these $p(e_i)$ values stop changing on average in time? We argue that this happens when equilibrium is established. Thus, one has a statistical conserved quantity in $p(e_i)$'s such that $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ does not change the conserved quantity. This conserved quantity, however, must implicitly contain $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N$ or whatever conservation laws apply a priori. We try to explain why : $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i p(e_i) + B \sum_i p(e_i) = 0$ ((1)) holds a priori, as we have used this in a number of previous notes. We argue that there must exist a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ in order that energy (and hence energy conservation) emerge and that one may consider a statistical conserved quantity in terms of average values. Thus, one may try: $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. In the FD and BE cases, there are multiple probabilities (2), so two terms are needed. Ultimately there is still an $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ which emerges from the $dG(p(e_i))$ expression. In the Tsallis case, for which there is no immediate reaction balance or $\ln(\text{number of states})$ factorial expression using Stirling's approximation, the above idea still holds, but one uses $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E/N$ as the physical constraints. Thus, the idea of ((1)) seems to be a powerful approach to finding equilibrium $p(e_i)$ values, but does not need to be based on reaction balance or factorial (\ln number of states) schemes. It may be introduced a priori as described above, we argue.